

A Study on Issues and Algorithms of Cyber Security

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Abstract:-

Cyber Security plays a vital role in today's Digital Era. Security is the necessity in social media, apps, organizations and many other digital platforms to avoid data breaches and attacks of data that are involved in that area. Cyber is a vast space in the field of Information Technology which adopts computing, processing, transmitting and many more operations over the Web. To secure this space which includes audio, video, text, graphics etc, several approaches are used. This paper makes an attempt to brief on the issues and resolutions adopted for a better secured cyber environment.

Keywords:- Cyber, Information Technology, Data Breaches, Attacks.

I. Introduction

To provide security for the web, cyber security agencies are spread across the world to minimize phishing, tampering, spoofing, social engineering, privilege escalation, malware attacks and so on. Cyber security involves defending of the networks, applications, information, operations etc over the net. As per a risk based security report related to cyber security, more than 7.9 billion records are attacked in the year 2019 alone [8]. To fight with the unwanted processes running in the cyber, cyber organizations across the world deploy continuous monitoring of all electronic resources 24/7. The cyber agencies try to resolve the issues related to cyber harassments, denial of services, vulnerability reports and many more to provide a better service to the end users by adopting various methodologies which are reviewed in this paper. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II has the Literature Survey; Section III presents the algorithms used for cyber security and finally the conclusion in Section IV.

II. Literature Survey

In the paper, reviewing cyber security social engineering training and awareness programs- pitfalls and ongoing issues, the authors have discussed about Social engineering which is a method that seeks to exploit weakness in human nature to get his/her personal details. The papers specifies on organizing awareness programs to the employees in an organization to develop the ability to recognize, flag, evade and disable malicious attempts of an attack. In the business environment, digital devices and network damages can take place. Manipulation based on governmental agendas in the form of spreading misinformation is a common method used by social engineers. Hackers and/or social engineering attack procedures use several up to date methods to obtain baiting, quid pro quo, pre texting and piggybacking. The users of the cyber without knowledge sometime leave their personal information and digital footprints which is the cause of cyber attacks [1].

In the paper, threats and countermeasures of cyber security in direct and remote vehicle communication systems, authors have discussed about the vehicular networking for intelligent transportation system (ITS). The system has VANET (vehicular adhoc network), a network which is wireless and can communicate with other vehicles. The information exchange in this network will be about the accident warning, curvature of roads, traffic condition. The paper briefs on remote keyless entry(RKE) system, wireless access in vehicular system, zigbee technology, Blue tooth Technology, wimax and wifi technology. The RKE system also called as remote control locking. The lock is controlled by a keypad. Several vehicle manufacturers are using cryptographic RKE keys. DSRC (Dedicated short range communication) is a 802.11 p based technology which provides security, communication between vehicles (bus,car). The DSRC also has a high speed performance with a operating frequency of 5.9 GHZ. DSRC has limitations when vehicular density is more. Hence the Long Term Evolution (LTE) and LTE advanced is used which is a 4th generation technology. The generations of 5G and 6G use the derivatives of OFDM (Orthogonal frequency division multiplexing) which provides higher data rates[2]. Zigbee is a wireless standard based technology for WSN(wireless sensor network) applications. The Zigbee based security has a AES(Advance Encryption Standard) based encryption system. The Bluetooth, wifi (wireless fidelity) and wimax(World Wide interoperability for microwave access) technologies are also used in vehicular communication. Wireless security protocols such as WEP(wired equivalent privacy), WPA(wifi protected access) and WPA2 (wifi protected access version 2), which are enhancements of WEP are used to provide security in Wireless networks since 2004.

In the paper, state of cyber security : emerging threats landscape, authors have briefed about malicious attack to exploit individual computers using malware, spyware, virus, Trojan horses etc. The paper highlights about the seizing of online bank accounts. The paper has the overview of the emerging cyber security threats such as phishing , email spamming, botnet, key loggers, social engineering, Denial of service(DOS), virus, worm. Phishing includes stealing of passwords, bank account details, credit card numbers etc. Botnet is a set of computers which are interconnected by cyber criminals to perform unlawful actions .Malware and spyware gathers information stored in any electronic device without awareness of the client. Key loggers access the keyboard information to gain the users data. DOS is an attack which smashes the host and causes a break in the communication with the rest of the system which are connected to the host. Virus destruct the machine programs, worm which are undesirable move from one machine to another. The issues include Social networking scams, android malware, malicious spam, phishing attacks. Malware targeting, landscape migrating to mobile application devices, targeting mobile users. The paper focuses on the Bad and Good developments. The Bad developments are the criminal activities growing in government and private commercial institutions, in big data, in internet of things and in the cloud storages. The Good developments are building up a strong international cyber policy, performing operations such as active cyber crime threat analysis, vendors using security patches etc.

The paper emphasizes on using countermeasures such as strong authentication, secured protocols etc to battle threats. Government and Industrial policies should be comprehensive and well planned to assess periodic IT security risk.

In the paper, a study of cyber security challenges and its emerging trends on latest technologies, the authors have discussed about the importance of security in the areas such as cloud computing, mobile computing, e-commerce, net banking etc... The statistics include fraud, intrusion, spam, malicious code, cyber harassment etc. The paper also discusses the areas where in cyber security is essential .The areas where security is needed are web servers, cloud computing, mobile networks, and social media. The cyber security techniques such as access control and password security, authentication of data, malware scanners, firewalls, anti-virus software are used to nullify cyber crimes. Few of the cyber ethics that has to be followed by every individual are not trying to send any kind of malware to other systems in the network, not sharing password, not sharing personal information, not to download insecure information. These kind of unwanted stuffs may get downloaded while downloading apps, packages, tools, games, video, audio etc.

III. Algorithms

Cryptographic algorithms are widely used to secure cyber. The algorithms protect the transactions such as encoding, decoding, authentication in the cyber from hackers and intruders. The cryptographic security categories are shown in Figure 1. The services are Authentication, Privacy, Integrity, Non Repudiation, Service availability and reliability [5]. Authentication is a process which allows the genuine users to access the data available in the network. Privacy is a process which provides end to end security from source end to destination end during communication, transmission and in many other network related actions. Integrity refers to the complete data. This integrated data over the cyber also needs security. Non Repudiation process gives proof of origin and integrity of data. Service availability and reliability process concentrates on providing uninterrupted services with high security to the end users.

Figure 1. Cryptographic Security Categories [5]

In the virtual global system, cyber security is needed in both wireless and wire lined systems. The main entity in cyber security is encrypting the data using the cipher text which secures messages from the sender end to receiver end. The security of messages is incorporated using security algorithms and these algorithms are being enhanced in a regular pace. The cipher text is an encrypted code. Once the sender sends the message, it will be encrypted (secure message), transmitted through the communication channel and will be decrypted (original message) at the receiver end. This cipher will make use of Symmetric Key which uses one single key or Asymmetric Keys which uses two keys (Public key and Private key) for the purpose of locking the messages. The larger the key size which comprises of bits, efficiency of the algorithm will be good. Figure 2 depicts on how the data from the sender travels through the channel in a secured manner.

Figure 2. Block Diagram of Cyber Security

Some of the methods adopted to provide security are DES/3 DES or Triple DES (Data Encryption Standard) is an encryption method developed during 1970's. The ATM transactions make use of this method to provide security to the users. Blowfish method/algorithm developed in 1993 is a symmetric key block cipher. RSA security algorithm first developed in 1982 which focuses on encryption and encryption standards to provide security. IDEA (International Data Encryption algorithm), first described in the year 1991 is widely used to secure bulk data. MD5 message digest algorithm, first published in 1992 used as a checksum to verify data integrity. The AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) is a block cipher algorithm, developed in 2001 to replace DES. The AES algorithm provides excellent security when compared with DES and 3 DES [6].

Security operation plays a vital role in application security, disaster security, information security, network security. Any application which has to be downloaded from the Google play store checks for the security constraint to protect the users from Fraud, Intrusion, Spam, Malicious Code. The Cyber Security R & D Center (CSRDC) established by U.S Department has several security technologies, infrastructures and algorithms [7] to avoid cyber terrorist's havoc.

The intelligent algorithms in cyber security include NIC (Nature Inspired Computing) algorithms, Machine Learning Algorithms and Deep Learning Algorithms [7]. The NIC algorithm has partitions of swarm intelligence and evolutionary algorithm. Swarm intelligence (SI), a computational intelligence technique focuses on the data travelling across the cyber, analyses and predicts the behavior of data. If any hacking or breach of data happens in the cyber, then the segment of swarm intelligence which is tuned with all possibilities of hacking, intrusion or breach is capable of handling the fraud which occurs

in cyber. The swarm refers to the intelligent honey bees, ants, birds etc which communicate among themselves to construct bee hive by honey bees, ant hill by ants and gathering food by birds. This natural intellectual process by the bees, ants, birds etc are learnt by the humans and the same is implemented in swarm intelligence algorithm to secure the web. The Evolutionary Algorithm (EA) is a genetic algorithm which is capable of handling stochastic data, which are random in nature. The word Evolutionary signifies the instance of the Evolution of Human Beings right from Australopithecus to Homo sapiens. With this concept, the EA was developed which rely upon reproduction, mutation, recombination and selection. All these processes which are in nature are applied virtually in EA. The machine learning algorithm train the cyber system with a predefined code and the code runs behind the system to provide security. The changes in the system will be taken care by the algorithm by understanding, analyzing the whole model and act accordingly. The machine learning algorithms have the capability to modify themselves to the changing needs in the cyber environment. Table 1 shows the comparison of algorithms.

Algorithm	Year	CIPHER DETAIL	
		Key Size/Digest Size	Block Size
DES	1975	56 bits Key Size	64 bits
RSA	1977	1024-4096 bit Key Size	*
IDEA	1991	128 bits Key Size	64 bits
MD5	1992	128 Digest Size	512 bits
Blow Fish	1993	32 – 448bits Key Size	64 Bits
3 DES	1995	168,112 or 56 bits Key Size	64 bits
AES	1998	128,192 or 256 bits Key Size	128 bits
Machine Learning	1959	Computational Intelligence Algorithms implemented in cyber security	
Deep Learning	1967		
SI	1989		
NIC	EA		

Table 1: A Comparative study on the Cyber Security Algorithms

IV. Conclusion

In this Cyber age, the importance of security over the web plays a major role. A wide number of algorithms are being developed in the fast growth of Information Technology to provide strong shield to all types of data which are being used in Internet. This paper has made an attempt to analyze an overview of the different algorithms that are being used in cyber for a better optimization in the world of computer networks. Though there are a lot of Cyber Security Algorithms, cyber hacking still exists. Hence, the researchers are continuously working on many more new versions of algorithms to defeat the action of illegal operations in the Network.

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